

Title: Music Recommendation system using collaborative filtering

Author: Darpan Aryal

Tools: Python, Jupyter Notebook, Pandas, Numpy

Submitted for academic evaluation | 2022

Note: "This project was submitted as part of academic coursework and independently developed by the author. It is shared here as a public educational resource."

Abstract

In this report, we study the general perception and documentation of the Recommendation system. This system is used in the Web in order to recommend an item to a user based upon a description of the item and a profile of the user's interests. Recommendation systems have become an integral part of e-commerce sites and other businesses like social networking, movie/music streaming sites. Recommendation system has a huge impact on the revenue earned in many of the businesses. Simultaneously they make user's life easier by reducing the cognitive load of searching through information overload. The main aim of the recommendation system is to recommend music to users based on the previous data of music ratings given by various users. It uses million song datasets. The recommendation system is developed and tested with different music categories in million song datasets. To start with, we analyze the brief description of recommendation System in general. Then, we discuss why recommendation systems are necessary for Users in the present context and pin out the problems and try to solve them. Furthermore, we will focus on techniques used in the music recommendation system in order to create a model of the user's interests. The report also showcases similar systems that have been developed. Moreover, the report discusses the algorithms being used to create the module and the whole analysis of the work. In the end, we conclude with some ideas for further development and research.

Table of Contents

Table of Figures	5
1. Introduction	5
1.1. Explanation of the topic/ AI concept used	7
Recommendation System.....	7
Some of the Examples of Recommendation System.....	7
1.2. Explanation/introduction of the chosen problem domain/topic	10
2. Background.....	12
2.1. Research work done on the chosen topic/problem domain.....	12
Content Based Methods	13
Hybrid Based Methods	13
Similar projects using some methods	14
2.2. Review and analysis of existing work in the problem domain	16
3. Solution	16
3.1. Explanation of the proposed solution/approach to solving the problem	16
3.2. Explanation of the AI algorithm/algorithms used	17
Collaborative Filtering	17
User Based Collaborative Filtering	18
Item Based Collaborative Filtering.....	19
Advantages of collaborative filtering	20
Disadvantages of collaborative filtering	21
Singular Value Decomposition	21
Pearson's Correlation Coefficient	22
3.3. Algorithm of AI Used.....	22
3.4. Pseudocode of the solution.....	23
3.5. Diagrammatic representations of the solution	26
3.6. Development Process.....	27
Anaconda.....	27
Jupyter Notebook.....	27
Python Libraries Used	28
3.7. Achieved Results.....	28
Importing Modules	28
Loading the Datasets.....	29

Combining the Data	29
Data Preprocessing	29
Creating new features combining title and artist name	29
Taking the sample of the songs and sum of listen count of the songs	30
Displaying Popular Songs	31
Displaying User Song History	32
Recommending song for the user.....	32
Giving related songs based on the words.....	33
4. Conclusion	34
4.1. Analysis of the work done	34
4.2. How the solution addresses real world problems.....	35
4.3. Further Work	36
References.....	37
Bibliography	38

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Clicks on Actions genre and recommended popular items	8
Figure 2: Showing genre of movies what user want to watch	9
Figure 3: Clicked on recommended genre	9
Figure 4: Suggested popular songs of the genre	10
Figure 5: Recommended shoes by brand, price	11
Figure 6: Shown similar brands of a chosen item	11
Figure 7: Different types of recommendation system methods	14
Figure 8: Content based filtration method used by Jango	15
Figure 9: Collaborative filtering method used by Spotify	16
Figure 10: Hybrid Filtering method used by Mix Cloud	16
Figure 11: Collaborative filtering and its types	19
Figure 12: Figure showing User Based Collaborative Filtering	20
Figure 13: Figure showing Item based collaborative filtering	21
Figure 14: Diagrammatic representation of the solution	28
Figure 15: Importing Modules	30
Figure 16: Loading the Datasets	31
Figure 17: Combining the data	31
Figure 18: Data Preprocessing	32
Figure 19: Taking the sample of the songs and sum of listen count of the songs	32
Figure 20: Displaying Popular Songs	33
Figure 21: Popular song displayed	33
Figure 22: Displaying User Song History	34
Figure 23: Recommending song for the user	34
Figure 24: Giving related songs based on the words	35

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technique of writing computer programs, robot, or another device to think like a smart human. AI is the study of how the human mind thinks, learns, makes decisions, and works to solve problems. Finally, this research generates intelligent software systems. The goal of artificial intelligence is to improve computer functions that are linked to human intelligence, such as reasoning, learning, and problem-solving. There are several applications of AI: (Selvamanikkam, 2018)

Gaming: artificial intelligence (AI) plays a vital role in allowing machines to consider a vast number of viable positions based on deep knowledge. Chess, river crossings, N-queens challenges, and so on.

Natural Language Processing: Interact with a machine that understands natural language spoken by humans through Natural Language Processing.

Expert Systems: Machines or software that provide users with explanations and guidance.

Visions Systems: Systems that comprehend, explain, and characterize visual input on the computer are known as vision systems.

Voice Recognition: Some AI-based speech recognition systems can hear and articulate sentences, as well as grasp their meanings, while a person converses with it. Siri and Google Assistant, for example.

Handwriting Recognition: Handwriting recognition software reads handwritten text on paper, recognizes letter shapes, and converts it into editable text.

Intelligent Robots: Robots can carry out human-given instructions. (Selvamanikkam, 2018)

1.1. Explanation of the topic/ AI concept used

Recommendation System

A recommendation system is a type of information filtering system that attempts to guess how well a user might rate or prefer an item. In basic terms, it's an algorithm that proposes goods to people that are relevant to them. For example, on Netflix, which movie to watch, in e-commerce, which product to buy, on Kindle, which book to read, in Spotify, which song to listen and so on. (Agrawal, 2021)

Some of the Examples of Recommendation System

Netflix

Figure 1: Clicks on Actions genre and recommended popular items

Figure 2: Showing genre of movies what user want to watch

Spotify

Figure 3: Clicked on recommended genre

Figure 4: Suggested popular songs of the genre

Figure 5: Recommended shoes by brand, price

Figure 6: Shown similar brands of a chosen item

1.2. Explanation/introduction of the chosen problem domain/topic

The chosen topic of this project to build is Music Recommendation System. Everyone's musical tastes are different, which implies that no matter what music you create, someone

Artificial Intelligence will like listening to it. While the music industry may promote certain genres of music over others, it is crucial to remember that no human culture on the planet has ever existed without music. Whether we are famous recording artists, karaoke singers, or simply music fans, music is beneficial to us. The number of songs available far outnumbers anyone's ability to listen to them all. There are at least 97 million songs, according to MarsBands.com. These are the only songs that have been officially released. Since the website is unlikely to feature Happy Birthday or a nameless song from 1400 A.D. We would reach 200 million songs if we included songs that everyone knows or extremely old Celtic melodies with no names. This is the time when we act. (Kathavate, 2021)

Let's start with the assumption that there are around 1 million composers alive today that we are aware of. Using the same percentage as above, we may estimate that there have been around 15.3 million songwriters throughout history. Spotify has 4 million songs that have never been played. There must be billions of songs available, and Spotify is far from the end of the music world. What about all the CDs and albums that haven't been digitized during the last century? What about songs passed down the centuries in small African villages? There are trillions upon trillions of songs in the world, far too numerous to count, and the potential is enormous. More and an unimaginably bigger amount that have yet to be created, a universe of music for us to enjoy. (Kathavate, 2021)

Keeping this in mind, one might argue that a person's song collection is large, even if listening to music is his or her favorite pastime. People find it tough to choose from millions of tunes at times. Furthermore, music service providers want an efficient method of managing songs and assisting their clients in discovering new music through quality recommendations. This implies that it not only allows users to choose which music they want to listen to, but it also suggests songs based on their previous listening habits. As a result, an effective recommendation system is critical. Techniques for finding, retrieving, and recommending music content must be suited for music content to quickly access, discover, and deliver music content to the final user. In both academia and industry, there has been some work done to give music recommendation services. (Kathavate, 2021)

The goal of this project is to explain the current state of music recommendation and discovery systems, as well as to indicate the assessment difficulties that still need to be carefully considered and researched. A music recommender system is one that learns

Artificial Intelligence from a user's previous listening experience and suggests tracks that they might enjoy hearing in the future. Many music streaming services, such as Pandora and Spotify, are currently focused on developing high-precision commercial music recommendation systems. These businesses make money by assisting clients in finding relevant music and charging them for the quality of their recommendations. As a result, good music recommendation algorithms have a vibrant market. (Kathavate, 2021)

2. Background

2.1. Research work done on the chosen topic/problem domain

Artificial Intelligence has come a long way and is now assisting people in solving complicated challenges in their daily lives. The goal is to create a system that incorporates various sorts of algorithms and artificial intelligence to assist humans in completing various activities or problems. The topic I've picked for this research is a music recommendation system using collaborative method. However, it has been constructed

in the past using a variety of methods. The image below depicts some of the various methods/algorithms for developing a recommendation system.

Figure 7: Different types of recommendation system methods

Content Based Methods

One prevalent technique for recommendation or recommender systems is content-based filtering. "Content" refers to the characteristics or content of the items you prefer. The algorithm uses your characteristics and preferences to make suggestions for things you might like. It takes the information you offer via the internet and the information they can obtain and arranges recommendations based on it. The purpose of content-based filtering is to categorize products using specific keywords, learn what the client likes, look up those phrases in the database, and then suggest comparable items. (analyticsteps, 2021)

Hybrid Based Methods

Hybrid filtering techniques integrate several recommendation strategies to provide greater system optimization and avoid the shortcomings and difficulties of pure recommendation systems. Hybrid techniques work on the concept that a mix of algorithms can produce more precise and efficient recommendations than a single algorithm since one program's flaws will be addressed by another algorithm. Using numerous recommendation strategies in a combined model will overcome the limits of each strategy alone. Combining techniques can be done in any of the following ways: Using some content-based filtering

Artificial Intelligence in a collaborative technique, using some collaborative filtering in a content-based approach, and building a single recommendation framework that combines all approaches. (Chang, 2017)

Similar projects using some methods

Figure 8: Content based filtration method used by Jango

Figure 9: Collaborative filtering method used by Spotify

Figure 10: Hybrid Filtering method used by Mix Cloud

2.2. Review and analysis of existing work in the problem domain

Recommender systems are machine learning systems that aid in the discovery of new products and services by users. When you shop online, a recommendation system directs you to the product that is most likely to be purchased. Users are sometimes confused by choice and require help identifying what they're looking for, therefore recommender systems are an important component in our digital age. Customers will be happier, and sales will increase as a result. Recommender systems are like salesperson who know what you like based on your previous and preferences. (Shetty, 2019)

We are all aware that in order to 'recommend' an object, which may be a product such as apparel, or films, utilities, etc., a recommender system seeks to predict a user's interest. Recommending systems have become highly relevant nowadays due to the addition of alternatives in every sector, and they assist businesses better position their goods or services for higher mobility. (Shetty, 2019)

3. Solution

3.1. Explanation of the proposed solution/approach to solving the problem

The main goal of this project is to create a music recommendation system. Based on an examination of their involvement during use, the system will determine the musical tastes of users. In this approach, it is feasible to predict which artist or group would appeal to the user at any time. We don't always want to hear the same musicians or genres; we all have our favorite bands, but occasionally a listener wants to be surprised and enjoy a new discovery. (Ferguson, 2017)

To be suggested, a music recommender needs a music library. This project provides an assessment of numerous music services and their features, based on musical information available online and provided by some (friendly) music services. These services give developers access to their music libraries, allowing them to contribute to the development of new apps. To get this data, a web component has been constructed that links to music service providers. Within the client web browser, the web system implements the necessary communication skills to utilize this information. (Ferguson, 2017)

This system makes music information accessible to users, allowing them to find new artists, albums, or songs. To accomplish this, a comprehensive review of the state-of-the-art in music recommendation was conducted, with clear highlights on the recommendation approaches employed in numerous systems that implement suggestion using diverse mathematical models. The user can browse music collections while listening to a song, album, or watching a video thanks to the interface's dynamic features. While using the app, users will receive information about their interaction habits (profiles) as well as personalized recommendations of goods they are likely to like. (Ferguson, 2017)

3.2. Explanation of the AI algorithm/algorithms used

Collaborative Filtering

Collaborative filtering uses the system's interactions and data from other users to filter information. It's predicated on the assumption that people who agreed on a given item's rating will likely agree again in the future. The idea is simple: when we're looking for a new movie to watch, we frequently turn to our friends for recommendations. Naturally, we put more faith in recommendations from friends who have similar likes to us. The so-called similarity index-based technique is used by most collaborative filtering systems. Several users are chosen for the neighborhood-based methodology based on their similarity to the active user. Calculating a weighted average of the ratings of the selected users is used to infer the active user. (Kurama, 2021)

Collaborative filtering

- **User-based collaborative filtering**
 - Based on users' neighborhood
- **Item-based collaborative filtering**
 - Based on items' similarity

Figure 11: Collaborative filtering and its types

In general, there are two types of Collaborative Filtering approaches that software and applications can apply around the world. The following are some of them: -

User Based Collaborative Filtering

Collaborative filtering can retrieve information that users might not normally supply because its conclusions are derived from implicit data. The user-based technique is the

first type of collaborative filtering. This method uses collaborative filtering to limit down users with comparable habits, common contacts, similar demographics, and similar consumer behaviors.

Figure 12: Figure showing User Based Collaborative Filtering

This method is used by social networking sites to recommend people to other users based on their behavior patterns. The suggested friends' category on Facebook is an excellent example of this strategy. This category suggests persons users may know based on their virtual contacts and shared interests. (Rawat, 2021)

Item Based Collaborative Filtering

I have used Item based Collaborative Filtering.

Item-based collaborative filtering is a subset of collaborative filtering techniques that relates to the use of collaborative filtering to promote things or products. Items are

Artificial Intelligence recommended to consumers based on their historical data and interactive history by measuring product similarity and inferring related ratings.

Figure 13: Figure showing Item based collaborative filtering

Amazon developed and launched this type of collaborative filtering in 1998. Even today, e-commerce platforms like Amazon and Flipkart implement item-based recommendation systems to suggest similar items or products to users based on their previous interactive data. The technique of Collaborative Filtering in this approach works efficiently with the statistical technique of Nearest Neighbor and gives consumers with legitimate recommendations that have only led to an increase in consumption. (Rawat, 2021)

Advantages of collaborative filtering

- Collaborative Filtering Algorithm does not require large amount of external data and is easy to implement. (ipl, 2019)
- The recommendation becomes more personalized as it uses the as it uses social data as the friendship relation and strength of links between two or more user. (ipl, 2019)

- It is advantageous for both users and the providers. (ipl, 2019)
- Users do not have to waste time looking for requested things, which improves sales or hits for the providers. (ipl, 2019)

Disadvantages of collaborative filtering

- The main drawback of this algorithm is that it is memory intensive. (ipl, 2019)
- The amount of memory required to keep all precomputed disparities between item pairs preference values is proportional to the number of items squared. When you have twice as many items, you have four times the memory. Hence, it consumes more memory. (ipl, 2019)
- A collaborative filtering system may or may not succeed in matching items to one's choices automatically. (developers, 2021)
- There is a scarcity of originality and variety. (Staff, 2021)

Singular Value Decomposition

A factorization of a matrix into three matrices is called Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). It possesses some remarkable algebraic characteristics and communicates key geometrical and theoretical insights into linear transformations. It also has several interesting data science applications. I'll try to explain the mathematical rationale underlying SVD as well as its geometrical meaning in this article. (geeksforgeeks, 2021)

Singular value decomposition is a method of decomposing a matrix into three smaller matrices.

$$A = USV^T$$

Where,

- A is a $m \times n$ matrix
- U is a $m \times n$ orthogonal matrix
- S is a $n \times n$ diagonal matrix
- V is a $n \times n$ orthogonal matrix

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient

The test statistic Pearson's correlation coefficient assesses the statistical link, or association, between two continuous variables. Because it is based on the method of covariance, it is known as the best method for quantifying the relationship between variables of interest. It provides data on the magnitude of the link, or correlation, as well as the relationship's direction. (statisticssolutions, 2021)

The Pearson coefficient computation and simple linear regression are both methods for determining the linear relationship between statistical data. The two procedures, however, are not identical. The Pearson coefficient is a non-causal measure of the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two variables. Correlation, not causation, is demonstrated by the Pearson coefficient. Pearson coefficients range from +1 to -1, with +1 indicating a positive correlation, -1 denoting a negative relationship, and 0 denoting no relationship at all. (investopedia, 2021)

3.3. Algorithm of AI Used

Step 1: I've provided a direct URL so that my application may download the dataset directly from the website.

Step 2: Importing and organizing data from another data set

Step 3: Bringing the two datasets together

Step 4: Acquiring the most well-known song. This is performed by listing the song's title together with the number of times it has been heard. As a result, the higher the number of listens, the more popular/heard the music is.

Step 5: Making a Pivot Table is a simple process this assign value like listening count.

Step 6: Transposing The table should be set up so that each row is a column, and each column is a row. The T technique is used to transpose.

Step 7: Singular Value Decomposition is used (SVD)

Step 8: The Pearson Correlation Matrix is created.

Step 9: Inputting the song's name provides the index from the list indicating its place.

Step 10: Printing similar songs with a higher correlation

Step 11: Finally, on the console, print those songs that are similar.

3.4. Pseudocode of the solution

```
#Program Start
```

```
Start
```

```
#Input Section #Import Modules import
```

```
pandas as pd import numpy as np import
```

```
Recommenders as Recommenders
```

```
#Loading the dataset song_df_1 =
```

```
pd.read_csv('10000.txt', sep=" ")
```

```
song_df_1.head()
```

```
song_df_2 = pd.read_csv('song_data.csv') song_df_2.head()
```

```

# combine both data song_df = pd.merge(song_df_1,
song_df_2.drop_duplicates(['song_id']), on='song_id', how='left')
song_df.head()

#Data Preprocessing

# creating new feature combining title and artist name
song_df['song'] = song_df['title']+' - '+song_df['artist_name'] song_df.head()

# taking top 10k samples for quick results song_df
= song_df.head(10000)

# cummulative sum of listen count of the songs song_grouped =
song_df.groupby(['song']).agg({'listen_count':'count'}).reset_index()
song_grouped.head() grouped_sum = song_grouped['listen_count'].sum()
song_grouped['percentage'] = (song_grouped['listen_count'] / grouped_sum
)
* 100 song_grouped.sort_values(['listen_count', 'song'],
ascending=[0,1])

#Popularity recommendation engine pr =
Recommenders.popularity_recommender_py()
pr.create(song_df, 'user_id', 'song') # display the top
10 popular songs pr.recommend(song_df['user_id'][5])
pr.recommend(song_df['user_id'][100]) #Item similarity
recommendation ir =

```

```
Recommenders.item_similarity_recommender_py()

ir.create(song_df, 'user_id', 'song')

user_items = ir.get_user_items(song_df['user_id'][5])

# display user songs history for

user_item in user_items:

    print(user_item)

# give song recommendation for that user

ir.recommend(song_df['user_id'][5]) # give related songs based on the

words ir.get_similar_items(['Oliver James - Fleet Foxes', 'The End - Pearl

Jam'])

#End of Project
```

3.5. Diagrammatic representations of the solution

Figure 14: Diagrammatic representation of the solution

3.6. Development Process

Anaconda

Anaconda Navigator is a pc graphical interface that comes with Anaconda that allows you to run programs and manage conda packages, environments, and channels without having to use command line commands. (anaconda, 2021) Packages can be found on Anaconda.org or in a local Anaconda Repository using Navigator. It's compatible with Windows, Mac OS X, and Linux. (anaconda, 2022) Many scientific packages rely on certain versions of other programs to run. Data scientists frequently utilize various versions of many software and isolate these versions using distinct environments. Conda is a package manager and an environment manager in one command-line tool. This allows data scientists to check that each version of a package has all of the dependencies it needs and functions properly. Navigator is a point-and-click interface for working with packages and environments that eliminates the need to type conda commands in a terminal window. It allows you to search for packages, install them in an environment, execute them, and update them all from within Navigator. (anaconda, 2022)

Jupyter Notebook

The original web application for producing and sharing computational documents is Jupyter Notebook. It provides a straightforward, simplified, and document-focused environment. (jupyter, 2022) The Jupyter Notebook App is a web-based server-client tool for editing and running notebook papers. The Jupyter Notebook App can be run locally on a computer without internet access (as explained in this paper) or remotely on a server and accessible via the internet. The Jupyter Notebook App contains a "Dashboard" (Notebook Dashboard), a "control panel" that shows local files and allows you to open notebook documents or shut down their kernels, in addition to displaying/editing/running notebook documents. (jupyter-notebook-, 2022)

Python Libraries Used

Python's standard library is extensive, providing a wide range of services, as evidenced by the lengthy chapter-by-chapter guide provided below. The library provides worked-in modules (written in C) that provide access to framework functionality, such as document I/O, which would otherwise be prohibited to Python in some way.

Software engineers, similar to Python modules that provide formalized solutions to some common programming challenges. Some of these modules are specifically designed to help and improve the portability of Python programs by abstracting frequently occurring stage points of interest into stage agnostic APIs. Pandas and Numpy are two Python libraries used in the development process. The Pandas library is one of the most popular data manipulation and analysis tools among data scientists. Pandas data structures are meant to make real-world data processing much easier. They are quick, versatile, and expressive. Numpy (short for Numerical Python) is a library that consists of multidimensional array objects and a set of procedures for manipulating them. Numpy allows you to perform mathematical and logical operations on arrays. (educba, 2022)

3.7. Achieved Results

Importing Modules

Dataset Information

Million Songs Dataset contains of two files: triplet_file and metadata_file. The triplet_file contains user_id, song_id and listen time. The metadata_file contains song_id, title, release, year and artist_name. Million Songs Dataset is a mixture of song from various website with the rating that users gave after listening to the song.

There are 3 types of recommendation system: content-based, collaborative and popularity.

Import modules

```
In [1]: import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import Recommenders as Recommenders
```

Figure 15: Importing Modules

Loading the Datasets

Loading the dataset

```
In [2]: song_df_1 = pd.read_csv('10000.txt', sep=" ")
song_df_1.head()
```

```
Out[2]:
```

	user_id	song_id	listen_count
0	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOAKIMP12A8C130995	1
1	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBBMDR12A8C13253B	2
2	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBXHDL12A81C204C0	1
3	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBYHAJ12A6701BF1D	1
4	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SODACBL12A8C13C273	1

```
In [3]: song_df_2 = pd.read_csv('song_data.csv')
song_df_2.head()
```

```
Out[3]:
```

	song_id	title	release	artist_name	year
0	SOQMMHC12AB0180CB8	Silent Night	Monster Ballads X-Mas	Faster Pussy cat	2003
1	SOVFAK12A8C1350D9	Tanssi vaan	Karkuteilla	Karkkiautomaatti	1995
2	SOGTUKN12AB017F4F1	No One Could Ever	Butter	Hudson Mohawke	2006
3	SOBNYVR12A8C13558C	Si Vos Querés	De Culo	Yerba Brava	2003
4	SOHSBXH12A8C13B0DF	Tangle Of Aspens	Rene Ablaze Presents Winter Sessions	Der Mystic	0

Figure 16: Loading the Datasets

Combining the Data

```
In [4]: # combine both data
song_df = pd.merge(song_df_1, song_df_2.drop_duplicates(['song_id']), on='song_id', how='left')
song_df.head()
```

```
Out[4]:
```

	user_id	song_id	listen_count	title	release	artist_name	year
0	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOAKIMP12A8C130995	1	The Cove	Thicker Than Water	Jack Johnson	0
1	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBBMDR12A8C13253B	2	Entre Dos Aguas	Flamenco Para Niños	Paco De Lucia	1976
2	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBXHDL12A81C204C0	1	Stronger	Graduation	Kanye West	2007
3	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBYHAJ12A6701BF1D	1	Constellations	In Between Dreams	Jack Johnson	2005
4	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SODACBL12A8C13C273	1	Learn To Fly	There Is Nothing Left To Lose	Foo Fighters	1999

```
In [6]: print(len(song_df_1), len(song_df_2))

2000000 1000000
```

```
In [5]: len(song_df)
```

```
Out[5]: 2000000
```

Figure 17: Combining the data

Data Preprocessing

Creating new features combining title and artist name

Data Preprocessing

```
In [37]: # creating new feature combining title and artist name
song_df['song'] = song_df['title']+' - '+song_df['artist_name']
song_df.head()
```

```
Out[37]:
```

	user_id	song_id	listen_count	title	release	artist_name	year	song
0	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOAKIMP12A8C130995	1	The Cove	Thicker Than Water	Jack Johnson	0	The Cove - Jack Johnson
1	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBBMDR12A8C13253B	2	Entre Dos Aguas	Flamenco Para Niños	Paco De Lucia	1976	Entre Dos Aguas - Paco De Lucia
2	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBXHDL12A81C204C0	1	Stronger	Graduation	Kanye West	2007	Stronger - Kanye West
3	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SOBYHAJ12A6701BF1D	1	Constellations	In Between Dreams	Jack Johnson	2005	Constellations - Jack Johnson
4	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	SODACBL12A8C13C273	1	Learn To Fly	There Is Nothing Left To Lose	Foo Fighters	1999	Learn To Fly - Foo Fighters

Figure 18: Data Preprocessing

Taking the sample of the songs and sum of listen count of the songs

```
In [38]: # taking top 10k samples for quick results
song_df = song_df.head(10000)
```

```
In [39]: # cumulative sum of listen count of the songs
song_grouped = song_df.groupby(['song']).agg({'listen_count': 'count'}).reset_index()
song_grouped.head()
```

```
Out[39]:
```

	song	listen_count
0	#40 - DAVE MATTHEWS BAND	1
1	& Down - Boys Noize	4
2	'97 Bonnie & Clyde - Eminem	2
3	'Round Midnight - Miles Davis	3
4	'Till I Collapse - Eminem / Nate Dogg	6

```
In [40]: grouped_sum = song_grouped['listen_count'].sum()
song_grouped['percentage'] = (song_grouped['listen_count'] / grouped_sum) * 100
song_grouped.sort_values(['listen_count', 'song'], ascending=[0,1])
```

```
Out[40]:
```

	song	listen_count	percentage
3660	Sehr kosmisch - Harmonia	45	0.45
4678	Undo - Björk	32	0.32
5105	You're The One - Dwight Yoakam	32	0.32
1071	Dog Days Are Over (Radio Edit) - Florence + Th...	28	0.28
3655	Secrets - OneRepublic	28	0.28
...
5139	high fives - Four Tet	1	0.01
5140	in white rooms - Booka Shade	1	0.01
5143	paranoid android - Christopher O'Riley	1	0.01

Figure 19: Taking the sample of the songs and sum of listen count of the songs

Displaying Popular Songs

Popularity Recommendation Engine

```
In [41]: pr = Recommenders.popularity_recommender_py()
```

```
In [42]: pr.create(song_df, 'user_id', 'song')
```

```
In [43]: # display the top 10 popular songs
pr.recommend(song_df['user_id'])[5]
```

```
Out[43]:
```

	user_id	song	score	Rank
3660	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Sehr kosmisch - Harmonia	45	1.0
4678	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Undo - Björk	32	2.0
5105	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	You're The One - Dwight Yoakam	32	3.0
1071	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Dog Days Are Over (Radio Edit) - Florence + Th...	28	4.0
3655	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Secrets - OneRepublic	28	5.0
4378	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	The Scientist - Coldplay	27	6.0
4712	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Use Somebody - Kings Of Leon	27	7.0
3476	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Revelry - Kings Of Leon	26	8.0
1387	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Fireflies - Chartraxx Karaoke	24	9.0
1862	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Horn Concerto No. 4 in E flat K495: II. Romanc...	23	10.0

Figure 20: Displaying Popular Songs

```
In [44]: pr.recommend(song_df['user_id'])[100]
```

```
Out[44]:
```

	user_id	song	score	Rank
3660	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	Sehr kosmisch - Harmonia	45	1.0
4678	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	Undo - Björk	32	2.0
5105	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	You're The One - Dwight Yoakam	32	3.0
1071	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	Dog Days Are Over (Radio Edit) - Florence + Th...	28	4.0
3655	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	Secrets - OneRepublic	28	5.0
4378	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	The Scientist - Coldplay	27	6.0
4712	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	Use Somebody - Kings Of Leon	27	7.0
3476	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	Revelry - Kings Of Leon	26	8.0
1387	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	Fireflies - Chartraxx Karaoke	24	9.0
1862	e006b1a48f466bf59feefed32bec6494495a4436	Horn Concerto No. 4 in E flat K495: II. Romanc...	23	10.0

Figure 21: Popular song displayed

Displaying User Song History

Item Similarity Recommendation

```
In [45]: ir = Recommenders.item_similarity_recommender_py()
ir.create(song_df, 'user_id', 'song')
```

```
In [46]: user_items = ir.get_user_items(song_df['user_id'][5])
```

```
In [47]: # display user songs history
for user_item in user_items:
    print(user_item)
```

The Cove - Jack Johnson
 Entre Dos Aguas - Paco De Lucia
 Stronger - Kanye West
 Constellations - Jack Johnson
 Learn To Fly - Foo Fighters
 Apuesta Por El Rock 'N' Roll - Héroes del Silencio
 Paper Gangsta - Lady GaGa
 Stacked Actors - Foo Fighters
 Sehr kosmisch - Harmonia
 Heaven's gonna burn your eyes - Thievery Corporation feat. Emiliana Torrini
 Let It Be Sung - Jack Johnson / Matt Costa / Zach Gill / Dan Lebowitz / Steve Adams
 I'll Be Missing You (Featuring Faith Evans & 112)(Album Version) - Puff Daddy
 Love Shack - The B-52's
 Clarity - John Mayer
 I?'m A Steady Rollin? Man - Robert Johnson
 The Old Saloon - The Lonely Island
 Behind The Sea [Live In Chicago] - Panic At The Disco
 Champion - Kanye West
 Breakout - Foo Fighters
 Ragged Wood - Fleet Foxes
 Mykonos - Fleet Foxes
 Country Road - Jack Johnson / Paula Fuga
 Oh No - Andrew Bird
 Love Song For No One - John Mayer
 Jewels And Gold - Angus & Julia Stone

Figure 22: Displaying User Song History

Recommending song for the user

```
NOTES TO HEAVEN - JACK JOHNSON
```

```
In [48]: # give song recommendation for that user
ir.recommend(song_df['user_id'][5])
```

No. of unique songs for the user: 45
 no. of unique songs in the training set: 5151
 Non zero values in coocurrence_matrix :6844

```
Out[48]:
```

	user_id	song	score	rank
0	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Oliver James - Fleet Foxes	0.043076	1
1	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Quiet Houses - Fleet Foxes	0.043076	2
2	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Your Protector - Fleet Foxes	0.043076	3
3	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Tiger Mountain Peasant Song - Fleet Foxes	0.043076	4
4	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Sun It Rises - Fleet Foxes	0.043076	5
5	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	The End - Pearl Jam	0.037531	6
6	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	St. Elsewhere - Dave Grusin	0.037531	7
7	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Misled - Céline Dion	0.037531	8
8	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Oil And Water - Incubus	0.037531	9
9	b80344d063b5ccb3212f76538f3d9e43d87dca9e	Meadowlarks - Fleet Foxes	0.037531	10

Figure 23: Recommending song for the user

Giving related songs based on the words

```
In [51]: # give related songs based on the words  
ir.get_similar_items(['Oliver James - Fleet Foxes', 'The End - Pearl Jam'])
```

```
no. of unique songs in the training set: 5151  
Non zero values in cooccurrence_matrix :75
```

```
Out[51]:
```

user_id	song	score	rank
0	Quiet Houses - Fleet Foxes	0.75	1
1	St. Elsewhere - Dave Grusin	0.75	2
2	Misled - Céline Dion	0.75	3
3	Your Protector - Fleet Foxes	0.75	4
4	Oil And Water - Incubus	0.75	5
5	Tiger Mountain Peasant Song - Fleet Foxes	0.75	6
6	Meadowlarks - Fleet Foxes	0.75	7
7	Sun It Rises - Fleet Foxes	0.75	8
8	I'd Die Without You - P.M. Dawn	0.75	9
9	Meet Virginia - Train	0.75	10

Figure 24: Giving related songs based on the words

4. Conclusion

4.1. Analysis of the work done

I was instructed to choose any AI topic for the assigned Coursework. Any chosen problem should be thoroughly studied, as well as a conceptual solution for the chosen difficulties developed. The solution must be described in detail, which include all relevant diagrams for the chosen AI topic. As an AI topic for this semester, I've chosen the music recommendation system.

In today's environment, recommendation systems have become a crucial feature on the Internet for users to express their preferences for brands. With the expanding number of users and products, recommendation systems confront two major flaws: data separate input and data adaptability, which result in poor prediction quality and inefficient time consumption. The project's tasks were all accomplished on time. The project's tasks were challenging for me to complete. It required a significant amount of research and study time. I'll have to put in more effort than I did on the prior job to finish this one.

This project is a little difficult for me to finish. There was a lot of research and study done on this topic at initially. Finally, the submission was completed after finishing all the given projects. This project not only completed all the assignments on time, but it also assisted in the development of knowledge, skills, and taught many things connected to this software that will be extremely important in my programming career.

This assignment provided me with a thorough understanding of a recommendation system using collaborative filtering while I was enrolled in this school. Overall, even though the tasks were excessively demanding and required nights of hard effort and labor, completing them was a lot of joy. As the project ends, I'd want to express my gratitude to our module leader for giving us with the task. Throughout this research, I learned a lot about artificial intelligence and how it has helped companies such as Amazon and Netflix propose stuff to their users. The material is developed after extensive investigation and consultation with teachers.

4.2. How the solution addresses real world problems

In a variety of methods, Music Recommender or Music Recommendation System is utilized to solve real-world problems. We are all aware of the importance and popularity of music in our daily lives. Songs and music make us happy, relieve depression, reduce stress, and improve our health. They also help us sleep better, among other things. However, not everyone's taste in music is the same. Country, hip-hop, metal, rock, rap, pop, and other genres are only a few examples. It's possible that I like Metal and the other person despises it. As a result, people's musical preferences may differ.

This Recommender system was created to address issues like these. Rap fans are given more Rap tracks to listen to instead of other music. This is like folks who enjoy different genres. This makes it very simple for individuals, businesses, and artists. Because there are millions of songs in the world today, with all kinds of genres, businesses can profit if customers find music they like. Recommending songs of people's choosing can also save them time. The main goal of this recommender is to help individuals find music that is close to their taste.

So, this recommender system helps both the user and the provider. It helps user to listen their favorite playlist anytime and easy to search the music they like.

4.3. Further Work

Due to a lack of time and competence, some functionalities were not implemented in the system. Future work simply refers to unfinished work that aids in the enhancement of the system with future features and functions. The code portion of constructing a collaborative filtering-based book recommendation system is left here. I will implement this recommended system on my future work and also I will use this for final year project as well which will help me to recommend things on my project.

References

Agrawal, S. K., 2021. *analyticsvidhya*. [Online]
Available at: analyticsvidhya.com [Accessed 19 Decembert 2021].

anaconda, 2021. *anaconda*. [Online]
Available at: <https://anaconda.org/anaconda/anaconda-navigator> [Accessed 24 January 2022].

anaconda, 2022. *anaconda*. [Online]
Available at: <https://docs.anaconda.com/anaconda/navigator/index.html> [Accessed 24 January 2022].

analyticsteps, 2021. *analyticsteps*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.analyticssteps.com/blogs/what-content-based-recommendation-systemmachine-learning>
[Accessed 19 December 2021].

Chang, X., 2017. *researchgate*. [Online] Available
at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319918936_A_hybrid_approach_for_article_recommendation_in_research_social_networks [Accessed 20 December 2021].

developers, g., 2021. *google developers*. [Online]
Available at: <https://developers.google.com/machine-learning/recommendation/contentbased/summary>
[Accessed 22 December 2021].

educba, 2022. *educba*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.educba.com/python-libraries-list/> [Accessed 24 January 2022].

Ferguson, C., 2017. *silotips*. [Online]
Available at: <https://silo.tips/music-recommender-system> [Accessed 21 December 2021].

Garg, S., 2014. *music recommender system*, Kanpur: iitk.

geeksforgeeks, 2021. *geeksforgeeks*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/singular-value-decomposition-svd/> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

investopedia, 2021. *investopedia*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/032515/what-does-it-mean-if-correlationcoefficient-positive-negative-or-zero.asp> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

ipl, 2019. *ipl*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.ipl.org/essay/Advantages-Of-Collaborative-Filtering-PCD9BMRAQG>
[Accessed 22 December 2021].

jupyter, 2022. *jupyter*. [Online] Available at: <https://jupyter.org/> [Accessed 24 January 2022].

jupyter-notebook-, 2022. *jupyter-notebook-*. [Online] Available at: https://jupyter-notebook-beginner-guide.readthedocs.io/en/latest/what_is_jupyter.html [Accessed 24 January 2022].

Kathavate, S., 2021. *IJERT*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.ijert.org/music-recommendation-system-using-content-and-collaborativefiltering-methods> [Accessed 20 December 2021].

Kurama, V., 2021. *builtin*. [Online] Available at: <https://builtin.com/data-science/collaborative-filtering-recommender-system> [Accessed 21 December 2021].

Rawat, S., 2021. *analyticsteps*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.analyticssteps.com/blogs/what-collaborative-filtering-types-working-andcase-study> [Accessed 21 December 2021].

Selvamanikkam, M., 2018. *becominghuman*. [Online] Available at: <https://becominghuman.ai/introduction-to-artificial-intelligence-5fba0148ec99> [Accessed 19 December 2021].

Shetty, B., 2019. *builtin*. [Online] Available at: <https://builtin.com/data-science/recommender-systems> [Accessed 20 December 2021].

Staff, U., 2021. *Upwork*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.upwork.com/resources/what-is-content-based-filtering> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

statisticssolutions, 2021. *statisticssolutions*. [Online] Available at: <https://www.statisticssolutions.com/free-resources/directory-of-statisticalanalyses/pearsons-correlation-coefficient/> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

Bibliography

Agrawal, S. K., 2021. *analyticsvidhya*. [Online] Available at: analyticsvidhya.com [Accessed 19 Decembert 2021].

anaconda, 2021. *anaconda*. [Online]

Available at: <https://anaconda.org/anaconda/anaconda-navigator> [Accessed 24 January 2022].

anaconda, 2022. *anaconda*. [Online]

Available at: <https://docs.anaconda.com/anaconda/navigator/index.html> [Accessed 24 January 2022].

analyticsteps, 2021. *analyticsteps*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.analyticsteps.com/blogs/what-content-based-recommendation-system-machine-learning> [Accessed 19 December 2021].

Chang, X., 2017. *researchgate*. [Online] Available at:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319918936_A_hybrid_approach_for_article_recommendation_in_research_social_networks [Accessed 20 December 2021].

developers, g., 2021. *google developers*. [Online]

Available at: <https://developers.google.com/machine-learning/recommendation/contentbased/summary> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

educba, 2022. *educba*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.educba.com/python-libraries-list/> [Accessed 24 January 2022].

Ferguson, C., 2017. *silotips*. [Online]

Available at: <https://silo.tips/music-recommender-system> [Accessed 21 December 2021].

Garg, S., 2014. *music recommender system*, Kanpur: iitk.

geeksforgeeks, 2021. *geeksforgeeks*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/singular-value-decomposition-svd/> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

investopedia, 2021. *investopedia*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.investopedia.com/ask/answers/032515/what-does-it-mean-if-correlationcoefficient-positive-negative-or-zero.asp> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

ipl, 2019. *ipl*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.ipl.org/essay/Advantages-Of-Collaborative-Filtering-PCD9BMRAQG> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

jupyter, 2022. *jupyter*. [Online] Available

at: <https://jupyter.org/> [Accessed 24 January 2022].

jupyter-notebook-, 2022. *jupyter-notebook-*. [Online]

Available at: https://jupyter-notebook-beginner-guide.readthedocs.io/en/latest/what_is_jupyter.html [Accessed 24 January 2022].

Kathavate, S., 2021. *IJERT*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.ijert.org/music-recommendation-system-using-content-and-collaborativefiltering-methods>
[Accessed 20 December 2021].

Kurama, V., 2021. *builtin*. [Online]

Available at: <https://builtin.com/data-science/collaborative-filtering-recommender-system> [Accessed 21 December 2021].

Rawat, S., 2021. *analyticsteps*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.analyticsteps.com/blogs/what-collaborative-filtering-types-working-andcase-study>
[Accessed 21 December 2021].

Selvamanikkam, M., 2018. *becominghuman*. [Online]

Available at: <https://becominghuman.ai/introduction-to-artificial-intelligence-5fba0148ec99>
[Accessed 19 December 2021].

Shetty, B., 2019. *builtin*. [Online]

Available at: <https://builtin.com/data-science/recommender-systems> [Accessed 20 December 2021].

Staff, U., 2021. *Upwork*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.upwork.com/resources/what-is-content-based-filtering> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

statisticssolutions, 2021. *statisticssolutions*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.statisticssolutions.com/free-resources/directory-of-statisticalanalyses/pearsons-correlation-coefficient/> [Accessed 22 December 2021].

Plagiarism Report

The screenshot shows a Google Docs interface with a document titled "AI CW 2". The document content includes:

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technique of writing computer programs, robot, or another device to think like a smart human. AI is the study of how the human mind thinks, learns, makes decisions, and works to solve problems. Finally, this research generates intelligent software systems. The goal of artificial intelligence is to improve computer functions that are linked to human intelligence, such as reasoning, learning, and problem-solving. There are several applications of AI: (Selvamanikkam, 2018)

Gaming: artificial intelligence (AI) plays a vital role in allowing machines to consider a vast number of viable positions based on deep knowledge. Chess, river crossings, N-queens challenges, and so on.

Natural Language Processing: Interact with a machine that understands natural language spoken by humans through Natural Language Processing.

On the right side, a "Summary" panel is visible, showing an "Originality report expires on 12 Mar 2022". It includes a "Count" section with a percentage indicator, and a "9% flagged content" section with a toggle switch for "5% cited or quoted content". Below this, a list of "Web matches (9%)" is shown:

- ijert.org (3%)
- analyticssteps.com (1%)
- python.org (0.9%)
- builtin.com (0.7%)
- sciencedirect.com (0.6%)
- anaconda.com (0.6%)
- jupyter.org (0.3%)